

POLITICAL SCIENCES

ENERGY POLICY OF SOUTH CAUCASUS COUNTRIES IN THE POST-SOVIET PERIOD

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ABSTRACT

In 1991, the three South Caucasus republics - Azerbaijan, Georgia and Armenia - which regained their state independence, faced new security problems. The new geopolitical conditions made it necessary to take a number of steps in the field of political, military, and economic security. In the first years of independence, although the issue of energy security was seen as a component of economic security, it gradually became clear that it was also a matter of political security. From this point of view, the study of energy security issues of the South Caucasus countries in the post-Soviet period from a historical-political aspect is relevant. The purpose of the research is to determine the energy security problems that the fall of the USSR faced the countries of the South Caucasus, and to analyze the factors affecting the energy security of these countries. One of the main tasks is to investigate what methods and means are used by Azerbaijan, Georgia and Armenia to ensure their energy security.

Keywords: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Energy Security, Georgia, Hydrocarbon, South Caucasus.

Introduction

It is impossible to imagine the history of the world for at least the last two hundred years without the production, processing, exchange of energy resources, wars fought for territories rich in these resources, signed contracts, agreements reached. Since the middle of the 20th century, energy security is considered an important component not only of economic, but also political and national security of countries. In the new geopolitical and geoeconomic conditions that arose after the collapse of the USSR in 1991, one of the main tasks facing the republics in the South Caucasus was ensuring energy security. The Republic of Azerbaijan had rich oil and gas resources, and the country had made great achievements in the field of energy resources production even during the Soviet era. Although there are oil deposits in certain areas of Georgia, they were not sufficient to provide this country with hydrocarbon resources. Armenia had no oil and gas resources at all. In contrast to hydrocarbon resources, all three countries of the South Caucasus have the potential to produce electricity, and during the Soviet era, the infrastructure was formed to use this potential.

Another point was that under the new conditions, many European states began to see the South Caucasus as a region that could contribute to Europe's alternative energy supply. If the main factor that increased the importance of the Azerbaijan Republic in terms of European energy security was the rich oil and gas deposits in the Azerbaijani sector of the Caspian Sea, Georgia and Armenia were located on potential energy-transit routes. The territories of Georgia and Armenia had an important geostrategic position for transporting the oil and gas resources of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Turkic states of Central Asia, and Iranian natural gas to the energy markets of Europe. But how did the South Caucasian states use the existing energy sources and the important position for energy transit? This is one of the main research questions.

Methodology

Although the issue of energy security is considered an integral part of the modern political agenda, it emerged as a political problem at the beginning of the 20th century, and attempts to define the term "energy security" from a scientific and theoretical point of view began in the 60s of the 20th century (Cherp vā Jewell 41). Although the term is often used, there is no universally accepted definition of energy security among members of the international community. In one of the most accepted definitions, the International Energy Agency (IEA) describes energy security as "the uninterrupted availability of energy resources at an affordable cost" (Our work on energy security). However, this definition includes subjective and difficult-to-measure variables, assumes only security of energy supply, and does not take into account the security of demand concerns of energy exporting countries. From this point of view, the energy security of the South Caucasus countries was evaluated in the context of factors affecting energy security and components of energy security, not in the context of any separate theoretical definition. Factors affecting energy security are mainly based on five factors: physical-geographical factors, costs incurred to ensure energy security, technological adequacy and political factors. Physical geographical factors mean the availability of energy sources in the territory of the country where energy security is assessed, as well as in bordering countries. The costs incurred for ensuring energy security should be understood as the costs incurred for the reliable production, transportation, processing and delivery of energy resources to the consumer, as well as for the provision of energy infrastructure and resources. Technological adequacy refers to the technical infrastructure used in the process of energy extraction, production and delivery to consumers. It is known that energy security includes not only the risks arising from commercial or political disputes with the main suppliers, but also the risk of technical failures of the energy infrastructure (Zachmann). Technological efficiency is not always directly proportional to the

costs incurred here. For example, it is possible that a country with low expenses for ensuring energy security in the current period may have carried out supply works on the basis of modern technological innovations in the previous periods and subsequently reduced the expenses for energy security. Finally, energy security is influenced by political factors, which include the state's relations with other states, conflicts within its territory, and internal political stability.

During the study, attention was paid to the factors affecting energy security, as well as the components of energy security. As is known, energy security has four main components:

- availability,
- accessibility,
- acceptability,
- affordability (A quest for energy security in the 21st century: resources and constraints).

The assessment of the energy security of the South Caucasus countries by the listed components has led to significant results.

During the writing of the article, comparative analysis and systematic analysis methods were used. Using the comparative analysis method, the energy security issues of three South Caucasus republics have been compared, and their similarities and differences have been highlighted. Primarily, a comparison of the management of energy security issues and related strategic approaches has been conducted. By applying the systematic analysis method, the energy sector of each country has been analyzed separately. This includes information regarding the use of oil, gas, electricity, and other energy sources, as well as the analysis of infrastructure and management.

Previous studies and results obtained

In the period after 1991, researchers from various countries have paid attention to energy security problems of the South Caucasus at the regional and national level in their works. The French researcher Samuel James Lussac, while studying the problem of ensuring Europe's energy security at the expense of the countries located in the "near abroad" of Russia, mentioned the role of the South Caucasus in the process (Lussac 607-625). It should be noted that the term "near abroad" historically refers to the states that were members of the USSR and regained independence since 1991. It is clarified from the fifth section of the foreign policy concept of the Russian Federation, confirmed by the decree of the President of the Russian Federation Vladimir Putin dated March 31, 2023, that the concept of "near abroad" does not mean only states that are members of the CIS and border with Russia. Georgia, which is not a member of the CIS, as well as Turkmenistan, Moldova, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, and Armenia, which do not share borders with Russia, are also included in the concept of "near abroad." (Концепция внешней политики Российской Федерации) In the works of Marcel de Haas, Andrej Tibold, Vincent Cillessen, dedicated to the geopolitics of the region, the question of the effects of the power games of states and organizations on energy security in the South Caucasus was discussed (Haas, Tibold and Cillessen 18, 25, 33). British researcher Tracey C. German has written a number of

articles devoted to issues related to the regional energy security of the Caucasus (Tracey 64-71).

One of the significant works written on energy security issues in the South Caucasus is "The South Caucasus - Security, Energy and Europeanization," edited by Meliha Altunişik and Oktay Tanrısever. This book explores developments in the countries of the South Caucasus – Armenia, Azerbaijan, and Georgia – since the EU included the region in the European Neighbourhood Policy in 2003. It considers issues related to energy, ethnic conflict, steps towards regional integration, and, above all, security – including the involvement of Russia, Iran, Turkey, and the United States (Altunişik və Tanrısever).

In addition, energy security issues of the Republic of Azerbaijan are discussed by Pınar İpek (İpek 227-239), Н.Намидов (Намидов 7-11), Georgia's energy policy Demuri Chomakhidze (Чомахидзе 78-85), Т.С. German (Tracey, Pipeline politics: Georgia and energy security 344-362), Liana Jervalidze (Jervalidze), Georg Zachmann (Zachmann) Armenia's energy security problems Elnur Kalbizadeh (Kalbizadeh 37-51), Katarzyna Kosowska (Kosowska 475-482) Sevak Sarukyan (Sarukhanyan 26-36), Hayk Markosyan (Markosyan 222-229), A. Markarov, V. Davtyan (Маркаров and Давтян 178-191) has become a separate research topic in the works of such authors.

What security problems did the dissolution of the USSR create for the countries of the South Caucasus?

As a result of the collapse of the USSR, the republics in the South Caucasus became independent subjects of the system of international political and economic relations, and the secret conflicts that existed in the region at different stages of history turned into an active military phase again, disrupted the integrated energy relations during the Soviet era. Armenia's occupation of Azerbaijan's territories, Georgian-Abkhazian and Georgian-Ossetian conflicts dealt a heavy blow to the integrated energy system of the regional countries.

From the mid-90s of the 20th century, Azerbaijan, Georgia and Armenia began to take steps to restore the destroyed energy infrastructure. These countries have determined where they belong not only from a geopolitical point of view, but also from a geoeconomic approach. The Republic of Azerbaijan has chosen the route of diversification of its hydrocarbon resources to the world market. In addition to the Baku-Novorossiysk pipeline, which allows the export of Azerbaijan's oil to the world markets through Russian territory, the Baku-Supsa pipeline was launched, and in the following period, the main export oil pipeline Baku-Tbilisi-Ceyhan was built. Georgia, located on the route of Azerbaijan's energy pipelines, started active cooperation with Azerbaijan and Turkey in order to ensure its energy and economic security. Armenia, which has rather tense relations with Turkey and Azerbaijan, chose a different path. He began to use the energy resources of Russia and Iran. Thus, Azerbaijan-Georgia-Turkey and Russia-Armenia-Iran axis were formed in the field of energy security in the region.

Although the indicators of the three countries were different in terms of energy supply, they had a number

of similar problems in the field of energy security. In the first years after the restoration of state independence, the energy infrastructure of all three countries was quite outdated and in need of modernization. Disconnection led to a decrease in per capita energy consumption in these countries. There was no normal infrastructure and legal basis for the efficient use of energy and the expansion of the use of renewable energy sources.

Energy policy of Azerbaijan: economic and political context

In the period after the restoration of state independence of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the issue of ensuring energy independence was treated not only as an economic but also a political issue. The conducted analyzes show that the physical and geographical factors affecting energy security were clearly in favor of Azerbaijan. The presence of rich oil and gas deposits both in the land area of the Republic of Azerbaijan and in the Azerbaijani sector of the Caspian Sea has allowed the country to ensure its own energy security, as well as realize its political goals by contributing to the energy security of some neighboring states and Europe. According to BP's June 2021 Statistical Review of World Energy, Azerbaijan's oil reserves at the end of 2020 amounted to 7 billion barrels, making up 0.4 percent of the world's total oil reserves. Azerbaijan has an estimated 2.5 trillion cubic metres of proven natural gas reserves, according to the BP Statistical Review of World Energy 2021. (Azerbaijan energy profile 16). On the other hand, the geographical position of the Republic of Azerbaijan has created additional opportunities for it to become a territory through which energy transit lines pass.

In the first years of independence, despite the lack of its own financial means to ensure the country's energy security, the Republic of Azerbaijan achieved great economic benefits by developing and implementing a long-term oil strategy supported financially and technically by foreign donors. In this direction, the policy implemented especially during Heydar Aliyev's time was that the number of companies and countries involved in Azerbaijan's oil and gas industry should be large and geographically wide (Ipek 23). This moment has given Azerbaijan the opportunity to always benefit from alternatives. In the following years, using these revenues, large funds were spent to ensure energy security. Investments made by foreign donors and investors in the oil and gas industry of the Republic of Azerbaijan have ensured technological development in this field, and the government of Azerbaijan has taken a number of steps to ensure the technological adequacy necessary for the country's energy security, especially since the first years of the XXI century. However, despite these steps taken, certain problems related to energy security have appeared from time to time. On July 3, 2018, an accident at the substations of "Azerbaijan Thermal Power Station" LLC in Mingachevir caused a power cut in 39 cities and regions, including the cities of Baku and Ganja (Mingəçevirdəki qəzannın araşdırılması ilə bağlı Dövlət Komissiyası yaradılıb). After that, with the aim of improving the infrastructure of electricity supply, considerable modernization works were carried out in this system from a technological

point of view. Despite such circumstances, comparative analyzes show that the energy security system of the Republic of Azerbaijan surpasses the other two South Caucasus republics in terms of technological adequacy.

Geopolitical factors have significantly influenced the issue of energy security of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The USA and Europe – Russia and Iran competition for the power struggle in the region has allowed the Republic of Azerbaijan to maneuver in the direction of ensuring energy security. Parallel to this, especially during the presidency of Heydar Aliyev (1993-2003) and Ilham Aliyev (2003), the Republic of Azerbaijan maintained the balance between the two power centers. The state of Azerbaijan tried to take into account the interests of the Russian Federation, which refers the region to its immediate security zone. All components of energy security - availability, accessibility, acceptability, affordability - have been ensured. As a result, since 1998, Azerbaijan has begun to independently meet its domestic oil demand, and since 2007, its natural gas demand. Thus, the state of Azerbaijan has turned oil and gas export into a means to ensure the development of other areas of the economy and realize economic diversification. Due to tension in relations with Russia, the oil and gas importing countries of Europe, which have serious threats to energy security, have tried to increase Azerbaijan's role in this direction. It is as a result of this that on November 7, 2006, the Memorandum of Understanding on Strategic Energy Cooperation between the European Union and Azerbaijan was signed, and on July 18, 2022, the "Strategic Agreement in the field of energy between the European Union and the Republic of Azerbaijan, represented by the European Commission Memorandum of Understanding on Partnership" was signed (Avropa İttifaqı və Azərbaycan). Currently, many European countries consider TANAP and TAP, which export Azerbaijan's energy resources to Southern Europe, as a way out of energy shortages. Despite the political ambitions of France and some other member countries of the European Union to exert pressure on Azerbaijan, collective Europe understands that ensuring energy security without Azerbaijan would be difficult in conditions of strained relations with Russia.

Electricity also plays an important role in the country's energy security basket. Analyzes show that Azerbaijan's electricity consumption has continuously increased since 2000. It is clear that one of the important issues in energy security is also the correct regulation of the level of energy consumption, as well as sustainable supply of energy resources. In order to regulate the level of consumption, the government of Azerbaijan increases energy tariffs from time to time. The Republic of Azerbaijan, which was an importer and consumer of electricity until the first years of the 21st century, has gradually turned into a net exporter since that time. Energy trade with Turkey and Iran is mainly based on trade to balance electricity supply to Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

Energy security of Georgia: main problems

According to territory and population statistics, Georgia is the second largest country of the South Caucasus. There are hydrocarbon resources in the territory of Georgia, albeit in small quantities. Georgia's proven

oil reserves are estimated at 35 million barrels, and Georgia's natural gas reserves are estimated at 0.30 trillion cubic feet, and it ranks 80th in the world according to both indicators (Georgia Oil Azerbaijan), (Georgia Natural Gas).

Due to the energy crisis in the 1990s, Georgia's energy consumption decreased and reached its lowest level in 2001. However, using the territory of Georgia as a transit for the transportation of energy resources of the Caspian basin has played an important role in strengthening the economic potential of this country, as well as in providing it with energy resources. The first agreements regarding the export of Caspian oil to the world market through Georgia were reached in 1992-1993. In June 1992, agreements were reached for the transportation of Kazakh oil, and in July, Azerbaijani oil to Oman via sea routes, passing through the territory of Georgia (Jervalidze 1-2). The "Contract of the Century" signed by Azerbaijan in 1994 with the oil companies of several countries of the world and the steps taken by the European Union to strengthen energy cooperation with Azerbaijan and Georgia since 2006 played an important role in increasing the importance of transit for the transportation of energy resources of Georgia. Many researchers believe that it was from that period that the South Caucasus began to become the central component of the network of transportation of hydrocarbon resources to Europe (Lussac 60). Thus, the physical and geographical factors have had a positive impact on the energy security of Georgia.

Georgia has gradually increased electricity production by using renewable resources on its territory. During the period 1997-2007 alone, electricity production in the country increased by 13.9 percent, and consumption by 4.1 percent (Чомахидзе 85). The country has now become an exporter of electricity, using its clean, renewable hydropower potential. Georgia not only ensures the transportation of Azerbaijan's oil and gas resources to Turkey and Europe, but also is the main route through which Russian energy resources are transported to Armenia. After 1991, Georgia tried to diversify oil imports to ensure energy security. Azerbaijan and Russia were the main countries from which Georgia imported natural gas. If in the period between 2006 and 2008, Georgia's energy supply was largely dependent on Russia, in the following years this indicator changed in favor of Azerbaijan. This includes the problems experienced in the energy supply of Georgia due to the explosions in the North Caucasus region of Russia in January 2006 (Haas, Tibold and Cillessen 18), as well as military clashes between Georgia and Russia in 2008 (Tracey, Corridor of power: The caucasus and energy security 344-362).

Over the past decade, Georgia has made significant progress both in improving the security of energy supply and in transitioning to a cleaner, more sustainable energy system. European integration policy and rapprochement with the European Union also played an important role in this issue. In June 2014, Georgia entered the Free Trade Area of the European Union and signed the Association Agreement. The Association Agreement was ratified by the European Parliament in December 2014. As a result, Georgia has chosen the

path of integration with European standards in terms of energy security. In October 2016, the Ministry of Energy of Georgia signed the Accession Protocol to the Energy Union Treaty, and the country's parliament ratified the document a year later (Georgia energy profile).

The analysis shows that the development of the energy sector has been achieved through the minimization of state intervention in this field, privatization, reduced and simplified licensing, and a liberalized economic environment. Thanks to the support received from the European Union, Georgia is trying to adapt the technological efficiency in the energy sector to the standards of the advanced countries of the world.

Energy security of Armenia: limited energy resources and current conditions

After the collapse of the USSR in 1991, the Armenian economy entered a crisis phase and the energy sector was almost paralyzed (Kosowska 875).

Its geographical position and nature have significantly influenced the energy potential of Armenia. Compared to the other two republics of the South Caucasus, Armenia does not have hydrocarbon reserves at all. The energy security of this country is constantly dependent on other countries, especially in terms of hydrocarbon resources. During the Soviet period, Armenia, which benefited from Azerbaijan's energy resources within the framework of the alliance for a long time, was deprived of it due to its occupation of Azerbaijani territories after 1991. In addition to the suspension of natural gas transportation from the territory of Azerbaijan, the partial stoppage of the operation of the gas pipeline passing through the territory of Georgia led to the complete bankruptcy of the energy system of Armenia. This resulted in the energy crisis of 1992-1994. In those years, Armenia's energy facilities on its territory produced only 10-15% of the electricity needed for the country's economy and population (Sarukhanyan 27). Later, Armenia was able to restore oil and gas transportation from Russia to Armenia through Georgia. At present, natural gas, nuclear fuel, petroleum products and a limited amount of coal are mostly imported from Russia.

At the same time, by developing relations with Iran, which is known as one of the countries with the world's largest reserves of oil and gas potential, Armenia tried not only to import resources from this country, but also to implement pipeline projects of Iran's hydrocarbon resources on the Armenia-Georgia-Black Sea route. However, this did not materialize due to Armenia's economic potential, the sanctions imposed against Iran, and Russia's interests in Armenia and the European gas market. For now, Iran only makes certain contributions to Armenia's own energy security. The fact that the oil and gas pipelines from Russia to Armenia pass through the dangerous and ethnically separatist regions of Georgia increases the importance of Iran in this area and makes it an important alternative to the security of Armenia's energy supply (Kelbizadeh 39). It should be noted that in the fall of 2016, the Armenian government signed an agreement with Iran on the import of natural gas and the export of electricity.

Armenia, which is dependent on the outside world in terms of hydrocarbon resources, instead developed electricity production using renewable energy sources. However, according to 2019 data, 40 percent of electricity produced in Armenia is still obtained using natural gas. Hydroelectric energy produced is 31 percent, and nuclear energy is 29 percent (Armenia energy profile).

Along with these, it should be noted that Armenia is the only country producing nuclear energy in the Caucasus region (Armenia energy profile). In Armenia, there are hydroelectric cascades on the rivers Bazarçhayi-Barghushad (Vorotan) and Zangi (Hrazdan). The number of hydroelectric power plants operating on two rivers is nine. Armenia is also the only country in the South Caucasus that produces atomic energy. Even though the Metsamor Nuclear Power Station, which was built in the Soviet era, continues to operate, the low cost of ensuring energy security and Armenia's expectation of funds for this from foreign donors do not allow full provision of technological adequacy. Metsamor nuclear power plant, built in 1976, is 32 km away from Yerevan, the capital of Armenia. During the Soviet era, Soviet scientists themselves objected to the construction of Metsamor. Because it was located in the tectonic region (Kelbizadeh, Geopolitical and regional analysis of the Armenia-Iran relations in 1998-2008 432). This creates environmental security threats not only for Armenia itself, but also for the South Caucasus and each of the surrounding countries. It should be noted that the operation of the Metasmor NPP, which consists of two blocks, was suspended during the Spitak earthquake in 1988 due to non-compliance with safety standards. In the following period, Armenia based on its need for electricity, restarted one unit of the NPP in 1993 after cosmetic works (Altikat, Argun və Bayram 2063). In fact, the service life of the station ended in 2016. However, Armenia managed to extend its license through various means. Due to the insufficient expenditure on ensuring energy security, Armenia is unable to realize the improvement of the infrastructure of the energy system and is trying to attract substantial investments for this. Armenian researcher Hayk Markosyan writes that Armenia's energy system is characterized by physical decline and obsolescence of the material and technical base. Despite a number of large investment projects implemented in recent years, most of the production facilities have been operated for more than 30 years, and there are even 80-year-old facilities in the national energy production system (Markosyan 226).

As for political factors, Armenia's occupation of Azerbaijani territories for 27 years and its isolation from regional projects by Azerbaijan and Turkey did not allow it to participate in any of the projects that strengthen relations with Europe in the field of energy.

However, Armenia adopted the Energy Security Concept and then the Energy Sector Strategy on October 23, 2013 in order to overcome problems in the field of energy security. From the content analysis of these documents, it is clear that one of the main goals of Armenia is integration into the regional energy system. After the 44-days war, which resulted in Azerbaijan liberating its territories from occupation in 2020, the

tendencies of normalization between Armenia and Azerbaijan create certain possibilities for the possibility of this in the future. If Armenia normalizes relations with Azerbaijan, it could gain the opportunity to revive its energy sources. In the future, pipelines facilitating the transmission of green energy produced in Azerbaijan to Europe could pass through Armenian territory. This could bring additional revenues to Armenia. For the formation of a branched system, only the southern neighbor Iran and the northern neighbor Georgia are not enough for Armenia. Another point envisaged in Armenia's strategic documents on energy security is related to the development of nuclear energy production, increasing the use of geothermal, biogas, solar and other renewable energy sources for heating. In 2020, the "strategic program document on the development of the energy sector in the Republic of Armenia until 2040" was adopted. The points mentioned in that document among the main priorities of the development of the energy sector are important in terms of predicting in what form Armenia intends to ensure energy security in the future. It is intended to make maximum use of the renewable energy potential, to strengthen the energy efficiency potential of the country as much as possible. For this, it is planned to implement a number of measures by the Armenian government. It is interesting that the government of Armenia has set as one of its goals the extension of the period of use of the second unit of the Metasmor Nuclear Power Plant as much as possible. One of the main plans of Armenia was the full realization of the construction program of the North-South Road Corridor along the Iran-Armenia-Georgia route (Republic of Armenia Energy Sector Development Strategic Program to 2040 3-5). With this, Armenia also plans to lay cross-country power transmission lines and to form a regional energy system with its participation. It is believed that the formation of such an electricity corridor along with the transport corridor can increase the geopolitical importance of Armenia in the region. Armenia is also doing this in order to form a step-by-step alternative to the construction of the North-South corridor of Azerbaijan from 2018 (Маркаров and Давтян 180). The fifth strategic goal planned until 2040 is the gradual liberalization of the electricity market (Republic of Armenia Energy Sector Development Strategic Program to 2040 3-5).

Thus, the above analysis allows us to assess Armenia's energy security based on four components. It becomes clear that in terms of the availability component, Armenia cannot be considered a fully equipped country like the neighboring Republic of Azerbaijan. If Azerbaijan has both rich hydrocarbon and renewable energy resources, the situation in Armenia is different. There are no hydrocarbon resources in the country, but there are other resources for obtaining energy. One of the most problematic issues in terms of energy security of Armenia is the availability, acceptability, affordability components. If we pay attention to the countries from which Armenia imports hydrocarbon resources, we will see that Russia cannot be considered reliable energy suppliers due to distance and the presence of a

third country in between, and Iran due to frequent sanctions. This calls into question the fate of Armenia in the other three components.

Conclusion

Thus, the analysis of the energy policies of the three republics of the South Caucasus in the post-Soviet period allows us to draw a number of conclusions. First of all, it is clear that the collapse of the USSR and the collapse of the single economic space have made all three countries face serious problems in the field of energy security. The beginning of the 90s of the 20th century can be characterized as a period of "energy crisis" in the history of all three countries. In addition to the collapse of the single economic space, the energy security of the countries was negatively affected by the struggle between the states with interests in the region, as well as the conflicts in the South Caucasus. Azerbaijan, which has been using its rich hydrocarbon resources since the mid-1990s, has carefully managed to ensure its energy security independently and has now become one of the important countries for the energy security of not only itself and some regional countries, but also Europe in general. Choosing Turkey as the transit route for Azerbaijan's energy pipelines, on the one hand, strengthens the role of this country in Europe's energy security, and on the other hand, further strengthens the economic basis of Azerbaijan-Türkiye political partnership.

The strategic position of this country played a more important role in ensuring energy security of Georgia than internal factors. Both geo-economic axis (Azerbaijan-Georgia-Turkey-Europe and Iran-Armenia-Georgia-Russia) formed in the South Caucasus in the field of energy cooperation in the post-Soviet period intersect in the territory of Georgia. It is true that Georgia is considered to be part of the Azerbaijan-Turkey-Europe geo-economic axis, but the territory of Georgia is also the most favorable zone for transportation of energy resources between Russia and Armenia. However, Georgia is against the strengthening of Russia's presence in the region. Russia has deployed troops to the Abkhazia and the Tskhinvali region, which legally belong to Georgia but are under the control of Abkhazian and Ossetian separatists. Consequently, Georgia uses energy resources of Azerbaijan and financial resources of European countries to ensure energy security. Armenia is the most difficult country in the region in terms of supply of hydrocarbon resources. There is no information about the existence of any oil or gas reserves in Armenia's territory. Due to long-standing territorial claims against Azerbaijan, this country has not had the opportunity to benefit from Azerbaijan's energy resources like neighboring Georgia. Both geopolitical and geo-economic factors have strengthened this country's dependence on the Russian Federation and Iran in the field of energy security.

The Republic of Azerbaijan is currently striving to become one of the leading producers of green energy worldwide. If successful, the country will also become one of Europe's main energy suppliers in the new era. Georgia also holds significant potential in this field. If Armenia normalizes its relations with Azerbaijan, it can

benefit from Azerbaijan's experience in the energy sector and attract Azerbaijani investment to facilitate the development of its own energy sector.

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